

BLOCKWISE DISTORTION MEASURE FOR LOSSY COMPRESSION OF MULTISPECTRAL IMAGES

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ABSTRACT

A new blockwise distortion measure is proposed to evaluate the quality of lossy compressed multispectral images. The measure is based on blockwise distortions which are calculated between the original multispectral image and the compressed/reconstructed multispectral image. The calculated measures with various compression ratios are matched to a visual scale which is based on the mean opinion score (MOS). The nonlinear weighting using neural network is used for matching. The results from the new measure are compared to mean-square-error (MSE) based measures, to two-dimensional blockwise distortion measure, and to picture quality scale for grayscale images. The multispectral images are compressed using multiwavelets, principal component analysis, and DCT/JPEG.

1 INTRODUCTION

Geoscience and remote sensing have been the main application areas of multispectral images but nowadays multispectral images are available for different purposes due to the development in the spectral imaging systems [3, 4]. Applications in quality control, exact color measurement, and color reproduction use multispectral information, since RGB color information is not sufficient. For long term storing or image transmission the multispectral images should be compressed. The compression should be such that the spatial and spectral quality of the reconstructed image is high enough for the application.

We use multidimensional multiwavelets for multispectral image compression and reconstruction. The multidimensional transforms for multiwavelets are similar to the scalar wavelets and these enhancements have shown good performance in the compression of multispectral images [6, 14]. We use also principal component analysis (PCA) and DCT/JPEG to observe, if the quality measure depends on the compression method. PCA is successfully applied to multispectral images [7]. The DCT/JPEG-method is a well-known method for the compression of gray-scale and RGB color images [11].

The quality of the lossy compression of the multispectral images is measured similarly to the gray-scale images: pixelwise, mean-square-error based quantitative measures like signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) or peak-signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) are used. For multispectral image coding a quantitative measure based on the percentage maximum absolute distortion (PMAD) was developed in [12]. The PMAD calculates the pixelwise distances between the original image and the reconstructed image.

There are qualitative measures for gray scale images and RGB color images [2], [8] but for multispectral images qualitative measures don't exist. In this paper, a new qualitative measure is proposed with the following properties: multispectral images from different sources can be used, quality measure takes into account both relative and absolute errors, comparisons between different sets of images are possible, independency of the coding methods, quality measure is based on the important features of the image, and visual inspection of the multispectral images agrees with the quality measure.

2 CONSTRUCTION OF THE DISTORTION MEASURE

The pixel-wise error measures are good for random errors but not for structured or correlated errors [2, 8, 10]. Typical compression artifacts include blockiness, blurring, and jaggedness of the edges and they require spatial consideration, which is based on the original pixel values.

A sliding cube of size $3 \times 3 \times 3$ is used to process the multispectral image and three components are computed for each pixel: contrast, spatial and spectral structure, and number of different gray-levels. The contrast measures, how each pixel differs from the background. The spatial structure (edges) of the image is blurred or jagged in compression. The number of different gray-scales in a block measures blockiness [1, 2, 8]. The final measure, Blockwise Distortion Measure for Multispectral images (BDMM), is calculated using these three components from the original image and compressed/reconstructed image. The matching of the BDMM to the visual tests is performed using a neural network.

The contrast is a local change in brightness and it is computed using standard deviation [13]. The first error component, the contrast error e_c for a block is computed as

$$e_c = \frac{(\sigma^o - \sigma^{cr})^2}{\max(1, \sigma^o)} \quad (1)$$

where σ^o and σ^{cr} are the standard deviations of the blocks from the original and the compressed/reconstructed image.

The spatial and spectral structure is the response to edge detection operations in a block [13]. For a three-dimensional $3 \times 3 \times 3$ block the three edge detectors G_i , $i = x, y, z$ are filtering operations

$$G_i = \frac{1}{16} \times \begin{array}{c} \text{c} \\ \text{b} \\ \text{a} \end{array} \quad (2)$$

where a, b, and c are filters adopted from Laplacian edge-detectors by modifying the two-dimensional detectors to three-dimensional ones. The second error component, the error e_s in the spatial structure is a sum of all the edge-detection operations normalized with the contrast value of the block,

$$e_s = \frac{|G_x^o - G_x^{cr}| + |G_y^o - G_y^{cr}| + |G_z^o - G_z^{cr}|}{3\max(1, \sigma^o)} \quad (3)$$

The third error component, the quantization error e_q , is based on the number of different gray-levels Q in a block,

$$e_q = (Q^o - Q^{cr})^2 \quad (4)$$

where Q^o is the number of different gray levels in a block from the original image and Q^{cr} from the compressed/reconstructed image.

The total errors E_c , E_s , and E_q between the original and reconstructed images are received by computing the average values of the blockwise errors e_c , e_s , and e_q over the entire images,

$$E_c = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (e_c)_i, E_s = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (e_s)_i, E_q = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (e_q)_i \quad (5)$$

where N is the number of $3 \times 3 \times 3$ blocks in the image, and e_c , e_s , e_q are as defined in equations Eqs. 1, 3, and 4, respectively.

The correlation between the computed values of the distortion measure BDMM and the visual tests was obtained using a multi-layer perceptron with back-propagation. The problem is a curve-fitting problem with three input variables E_c , E_s , and E_q and the goal received from the visual tests V ,

$$BDMM = f(E_c, E_s, E_q; V) \quad (6)$$

The function f is modeled by a three-layer neural network with 6 neurons in the hidden layer and one neuron in the output layer. The function f is obtained as the network weights and biases, which are then used to compute the BDMM for all images used in the experiments.

3 VISUAL ASSESSMENT TESTS

In the visual assessment tests, we used three multispectral images called AISA, AVIRIS, and BRISTOL. Each image was of size 256×256 pixels and they had 32 spectral bands. In Fig. 1 one band of each image is shown.

Figure 1: The original images, left to right: AISA, AVIRIS, and BRISTOL.

The spectral range of the AISA (Airborne Imaging Spectrometer for Applications) is from 649 to 747 nm [9]. For AVIRIS-image, 32 channels from 1 to 218 by step 7 were selected from the range from 370nm to 2450nm [15]. The BRISTOL-image is taken in laboratory conditions from a flower leaf using the visible spectral range from 400 nm to 700 nm [16]. In the experiments, compression ratios from 1.5 through 2,4,6,8,12,16,32,64, to 128 were used. For visual tests, we selected three spectral bands from each image. Thus, we had nine (three images, three bands) sets of images and each set had eleven images (original plus ten compressed/reconstructed) for comparison and grading.

The grading value for the original image was ten and the grading value for the image with the compression ratio 128 was one. The rest of the images were to be evaluated in the range 1–10. If the viewer didn't find any differences between two images, then the images were graded with equal values. The scale is similar to the MOS-scale used in [8]. To get the global grading for all the sets, the second comparison was done between sets from different images: the purpose of this is to match the scales of the different images. The grading of a single set from one image is given in advance and the two other sets are graded compared to this known set. The number of images in each set is now five: the original image and four compressed images. Only the image with the highest compression ratio should be graded, other three compressed images were for reference. The total number of sets in comparison is nine. The details of the visual assessment tests can be found in [5].

4 RESULTS FROM EXPERIMENTS

The original visual grading from 1 to 10 was normalized to the range [0,1] and an average was computed for each compressed image. The second grading let us modify the bottom level of the grading, and similarly all the grading values for that image were scaled. We used linear scaling: $v_{new} = 1 - (1 - v_{old})(1 - a)$ where $v_{old} \in [0, 1]$ and the target value $a \in [0, 1]$. The three values a from the second visual test were (0.100, 0.094, 0.103) for the AVIRIS, AISA, and BRISTOL, respectively.

The computed values E_c, E_s , and E_q and the gradings from the visual tests were matched using a neural network. As input we had 33 vectors with 3 values in each vector, and as output, there were 33 gradings from the visual tests. The weights and biases of the neural network were then obtained and they were used to derive the parameters for the BDMM as defined in Eq. 6. In Fig. 2 the matching of the computed errors and the MOS grading is illustrated.

Figure 2: The matching of the computed errors and the MOS grading.

The BDMM was compared to different quality measures, which were Peak-Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), the Picture Quality Scale (PQS) [8] and the two-dimensional blockwise distortion measure (BDM) [2]. The PQS and the BDM were applied band-wise to the multispectral images, and the global values were received by averaging the values over all bands. The results for the three test images are shown in Tables 1, 2, and 3. The Chui-Lian multiwavelets were used for the compression and reconstruction.

The BDMM measure should be applicable with different compression methods. We used two other compression methods to test the independence of the BDMM on the compression methods. The first method is based on principal component analysis (PCA), and the second is the standard DCT/JPEG for grayscale images and now applied to each of the bands of the multispectral image. For comparison purposes, we have included also the results from the multiwavelet based compression. Fig. 3 shows the results. All the methods were implemented using MATLAB software.

Table 1: The comparison of quality measures, AISA.

CR	SNR	PSNR	PQS	BDM	BDMM
1.0	Inf	Inf	5.00	5.00	4.91
1.5	39.81	56.78	4.53	4.82	4.71
2.0	33.73	50.70	2.97	4.58	4.49
4.0	27.10	44.08	0.96	4.18	4.28
6.0	24.83	41.80	0.53	3.98	3.92
8.0	23.57	40.54	0.38	3.84	3.52
12.0	22.10	39.07	0.25	3.60	2.90
16.0	21.19	38.16	0.16	3.41	2.60
32.0	19.16	36.13	0.00	2.96	1.87
64.0	17.17	34.15	0.00	2.62	1.20
128.0	15.15	32.12	0.00	2.30	0.85

Table 2: The comparison of quality measures, AVIRIS.

CR	SNR	PSNR	PQS	BDM	BDMM
1.0	Inf	Inf	5.00	5.00	4.91
1.5	53.14	66.98	5.00	4.98	4.88
2.0	46.20	60.03	4.60	4.60	4.78
4.0	37.47	51.30	2.53	3.53	4.40
6.0	33.57	47.40	1.67	3.24	4.19
8.0	30.92	44.76	1.15	3.08	3.99
12.0	27.55	41.39	0.81	2.83	3.60
16.0	25.40	39.24	0.57	2.63	3.33
32.0	21.10	34.94	0.15	2.15	2.47
64.0	17.99	31.83	0.01	1.85	1.62
128.0	15.85	29.69	0.00	1.69	1.04

Table 3: The comparison of quality measures, BRISTOL.

CR	SNR	PSNR	PQS	BDM	BDMM
1.0	Inf	Inf	5.00	5.00	4.91
1.5	49.10	53.07	5.00	4.68	4.34
2.0	43.91	47.87	4.93	4.36	4.12
4.0	32.41	36.38	3.43	3.16	3.32
6.0	26.54	30.51	2.45	1.83	3.20
8.0	23.62	27.58	2.04	1.16	2.96
12.0	20.67	24.64	1.77	0.99	2.24
16.0	19.16	23.13	1.67	0.96	1.68
32.0	16.60	20.57	1.74	0.92	1.00
64.0	14.94	18.90	1.85	0.89	0.78
128.0	13.75	17.71	1.86	0.87	0.70

5 CONCLUSIONS

A measure based on the visual perception was proposed to measure the quality of the compression and reconstruction of multispectral images. The quality of the compression was visually evaluated by a number of observers and the visual grading was matched to the model of the measure. PCA and DCT/JPEG were used as comparative compression methods to obtain information on how the measure depends on the compression method.

Figure 3: Comparison of the multiwavelets (MMW), DCT/JPEG (JPG), and PCA using BDMM. a) AISA, b) AVIRIS, and c) BRISTOL.

The PQS measure gave the value of zero even at the intermediate compression ratios for the AISA image, for the BRISTOL image the lowest value was 1.86. The visual grading gave about equal values for the two images. The BDM acted somewhat similarly to the PSNR between the different images.

The BDMM had more linear performance than the SNR/PSNR. The values of the SNR/PSNR measures degraded fast as the compression ratio increases and this was not in accordance with the visual grading. The theoretical maximum of the BDMM in Tables 1, 2, and 3 is 5.0, but due to the statistical nature of matching, the highest value received was 4.91.

At low compression ratios, the BDMM is similar for wavelet, PCA and DCT/JPEG based compression methods. At high compression ratios, different compression methods produce different types of errors and the current error components used in the BDMM should be further developed to better capture the distortions from different compression methods.

Three images with different visual appearance were used: AISA with regions of random, high frequency texture, AVIRIS with regions of regular high frequency textures, and BRISTOL with even regions of not so clear texture. BDMM performed most constantly over all the images.

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